

PERT estimate is an under-estimate - Visual evidence using Computational statistics

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PERT (Program Evaluation and Review Technique) is a statistical project management technique used to estimate the total duration or cost of a project. It leverages the Central Limit Theorem (CLT) to produce reliable duration/cost estimates for the project managers. It is thus helpful during project planning, financial bidding, and tenders.

Let's consider that a project's total duration has to be estimated. The project manager breaks down the project into n tasks. Each task's duration (in days) is a random variable, as no engineer would be able to give a single point estimate of the time required to complete a task. The total project duration, also a random variable, is the sum of all these n random variables.

$$\text{Total Project Duration} = Task_1 + Task_2 + Task_3 + \dots + Task_n$$

If all the n tasks are independent, i.e., an increase in the duration of one task should not increase the duration of another task, then CLT helps us approximate the total project duration as a normal distribution as n tends to infinity. Ideally, all the n tasks should also come from an identical distribution, but the Lindeberg condition relaxes that assumption as long as no small set of tasks explains most variation in the total duration. Once the total project duration is described as a normal distribution, the project manager can make reliable duration estimates using the mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of the normal distribution. They can be confident that there is a 95% chance that the project would be completed within $\mu + 2\sigma$ days. The same analysis can be applied to project costs as well.

Note: Independence of tasks doesn't mean one task should not wait for another. If the project is to construct a building, the task of painting can only be done after constructing walls. Task of constructing walls can only be done after laying the foundation. These tasks can still be statistically independent if the duration or cost of one task doesn't influence the other. But many real projects cannot be broken down into statistically independent tasks. If the cost incurred for the foundation is compromised upon, it could have greater upstream effects by necessitating thicker and stronger walls. In such cases, CLT cannot be leveraged and the total project cost/duration could show power law distribution [3], which can be built using Monte carlo simulations. There would be higher chances of project cost/duration escalations.

When each task is considered a random variable, it needs a probability distribution function (PDF). If there is historical experience or data about the tasks, then these PDFs can be assumed or constructed from data. Otherwise, three-point estimation is often used to build the PDF for each task. It involves asking experts or the project engineers to give three estimates for each task:

1. The optimum time required to complete the task (a)
2. The worst-case time required to complete the task (b)
3. The most-likely time required to complete the task (m)

Based on these three points, each task can have a PDF, either a triangular distribution or Beta distribution (scaled to [a,b] domain). Beta distribution is often used, as it allows for a wide variety of shapes [1] for different values of its parameters (α, β). The mean and standard deviation of the Beta distribution are approximated as

$$mean = \frac{a+4m+b}{6}; \quad std = \frac{b-a}{6}$$

Accurate mean and standard deviation of each beta distribution can also be calculated but PERT literature often uses this approximation [2]. Assuming independence of tasks, the PERT estimate of mean total project duration will be the sum of means of all Beta distributions of tasks. The PERT estimate of mean total project duration variance will be the sum of variances of all Beta distributions of tasks.

$$Mean \ Total \ Project \ Duration_{PERT} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_i + 4m_i + b_i}{6}$$

$$Variance \ of \ Total \ Project \ Duration_{PERT} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{b_i - a_i}{6} \right)^2$$

The above estimate works well when all tasks are performed in series, one after another. However, certain tasks can be done in parallel and their durations need not be summed up. The following project network diagram [Fig. 1] with 9 tasks [1] illustrates this:

Figure 1: Project Network Diagram

There are 4 paths in parallel in this project network: A-C-G, A-D-H, B-E-H, B-F-I. Each path has three tasks. To estimate the total project duration, the Beta distribution means of all 9 tasks need not be summed up. Path duration can be estimated for each path by summing only the Beta distribution means of all tasks in that path. The path with the maximum path duration is considered as the “Critical Path.” Critical path’s duration is the *Mean Total Project Duration*_{PERT}

Here lies the limitation of PERT estimation. *Mean Total Project Duration*_{PERT} is always an underestimation of the true mean duration of the project [1]. In the next section a simple one-step project is taken to explain this visually.

Visual evidence using Monte Carlo simulation

Consider the following project network [Fig. 2]. There are only two tasks (A, B) that can be performed in parallel and hence there are only two paths: A, B. From historical experience, the duration of these tasks is also constructed as normal distributions, but with different means. Task A can be completed in 7 hours, with a 3-hour standard deviation. Task B can be completed in 10 hours, with a 3-hour standard deviation.

Figure 2: A simple two-task Project Network Diagram

It is clear that path B is the critical path, as its mean path duration is the maximum (10 hours). *Mean Total Project Duration*_{PERT} would thus be 10 hours. But what about the true mean project duration?

Using Monte Carlo simulation, the above project is performed 10,000 times. The project duration at every iteration is the duration of the path that took more time, i.e., the critical path. In each iteration, the critical path varies. Despite having a higher mean, path B is not the critical

path in all 10,000 iterations. In about 2400 iterations, path A took more time than path B. The true mean duration of the project is thus the mean of all 10,000 project durations.

Figure 3: PERT mean estimate underestimates true mean when path PDFs overlap.

It can be observed [Fig. 3] that the PERT Mean Estimate of 10 hours, calculated from the critical path B, underestimated the true mean estimate. This is one of the limitations of the PERT estimation. The project manager relying only on the critical path from the project network diagram would underestimate the time required to complete the project. Overlapping PDFs of path duration cause this limitation. When PDFs of path duration don't overlap, the PERT estimation based on the critical path doesn't underestimate the true mean. [Fig. 4]

Path B is still more critical in Fig. 2 with a criticality index of 0.76. Criticality Index is the ratio of the number of times the path is critical to the total number of times the project is simulated.

Figure 4: PERT mean estimate doesn't underestimate true mean when path PDFs don't overlap.

To appreciate how wrong the project manager could be, consider the exaggerated case of overlap between PDFs of path durations [Fig. 5]. The fat tails in the Monte Carlo simulations show that the PERT estimation would severely underestimate project duration. For instance, based on PERT estimation, the project manager would be confident that there is a 95% chance that the project duration won't exceed 16 hours ($10+2*3$). But, based on the empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) calculated using Monte Carlo simulation, there is only an 82% chance that the project duration won't exceed 16 hours. There is also a long tail. PERT estimation would show a project manager that there is a ~0 chance that the project takes 20-25 hours. Monte Carlo Simulation shows that there is a 5% chance.

Figure 5: A exaggerated case of overlapping path PDFs

Figure 6: Empirical CDF calculated from Monte Carlo simulation

Conclusion and discussion

The PERT estimation is a handy statistical tool for project managers to build reliable estimates of project cost and duration. As long as the tasks of the projects can be assumed to be statistically independent, the Central Limit Theorem (CLT) can be leveraged to visualize the total project cost or duration as a normal distribution. If this independence cannot be assumed, the resultant distribution would have power law distributions with fat and long tails. Not considering the power law distributions would lead to underestimation of the risks involved with respect to cost and duration escalations. Monte Carlo simulations can be used to build resultant distributions when CLT assumptions cannot be guaranteed.

When tasks can be performed in parallel, identification of the critical path, the path that has the maximum path duration, is generally enough to estimate the total project duration. However, this would underestimate the true mean project duration, as other paths could also become critical by chance. The more the overlap between the probability distribution functions (PDFs) of paths, the more the underestimation. Monte Carlo simulations can be used to show the extent of underestimation. In such cases, the empirical CDFs constructed using Monte Carlo simulations will be of better use for a project manager to estimate project durations and risks involved.

Code to reproduce the visuals:[Link](#)

References:

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